

Lab-made RNaseZAP

Category Buffers & Solutions

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Version 3

Labels:

Step 1

This has been derived from the RNaseZAP patent from Sigma: For **2 L**

200 ml 6% Bleach (or 400ml 3% bleach)

20 g NaOH pellets

20 g of any dishwashing detergent (I use sunlight liquid - American equivalent would be Dawn Dish soap)

15 g Sodium bicarbonate

ddH₂O or DEPC-treated ddH₂O to a final volume of **2 L**

DO NOT AUTOCLAVE

Shake well before each use as some of the reagents might settle out with time.

Attachments

No file attachments

*This procedure was originally created by **Nadine Kleinhans***